

Constrained optimisation algorithms for population pharmacokinetic model discovery

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Abstract. Population pharmacokinetic (popPK) model discovery is a time-consuming process that can be significantly improved by using AI optimisation techniques to search the model space. Here we improve search efficiency by introducing constraints to avoid redundant areas of the search space. Evaluations on phase 1 clinical data show this approach reduces required NONMEM evaluations by up to 47% and search time by 18% compared to existing methods, without reducing performance of discovered popPK models. This constrained approach reduces computational cost & search time, aiding adoption of AI-supported popPK development.

Keywords: Population pharmacokinetics, popPK, optimisation

1 Introduction

Population pharmacokinetic (popPK) models are essential for understanding drug behaviour during clinical development¹ but can be challenging and time-consuming to develop². Machine learning approaches have been proposed to automate model building, often framing the task as an optimisation process to identify a configuration of model components within a predefined search space which best explains the data whilst remaining biologically plausible^{3,4}. Methods such as genetic algorithms and Bayesian optimisation are used to efficiently explore the space of possible popPK models, with candidate models typically evaluated using NONMEM (an industry-standard software). However, due to the hierarchical structure of popPK models, the model space can include large regions that are redundant depending on the model configuration. For example, popPK models often use a compartmental structure to represent how a drug moves through the body; these structures are typically developed using phase 1 clinical data. In a 1- or 2-compartment model, parameters related to a 3rd compartment have no effect and lead to duplicated model definitions. Despite this, many approaches represent a model for every parameter configuration within in the search space, regardless

of whether that parameter exists in that model, which leads to multiple states in the search space that all correspond to the same model. This redundancy reduces the efficiency of optimisation algorithms unless they recognise duplicate configurations, leading to increased computational cost and search time⁵. This problem becomes more significant as the dimensionality of the parameter search space increases. Such increases occur both due to drug system complexity (i.e. when modelling drugs with unusual absorption profiles or active metabolites), and from using generic model spaces which can be applied across a range of drugs rather than drug-specific spaces⁵.

To improve search efficiency, particularly in complex, generic model spaces, we propose a constrained optimisation approach for popPK model discovery. Central to this is an algorithm that identifies which features in the search space are active, based on the current popPK model configuration. By determining features that are actively contributing to the popPK model we can identify functionally equivalent models which have already been evaluated. We adapt both Bayesian optimisation and exhaustive local search methods to incorporate a constraint to avoid evaluation of duplicate model configurations. Our results show that these constrained algorithms significantly reduce the number of NONMEM model evaluations required, lowering computational cost and runtime while still identifying the same optimal model structure as their unconstrained counterparts.

2 Methods

Each model search is conducted within a predefined model space which contains many potential popPK models for extravascular administered drugs as detailed in our previous work⁵. All popPK models within the space are described by a 17-dimensional numerical feature vector which details various structural elements of the popPK model. The 17 discrete features, each with 2-4 possible values, result in over 800,000 possible feature vector configurations, which due to redundancy, represent 12,000 unique popPK models. Searches are performed using PyDarwin which runs optimisation algorithms to discover popPK models within the parameter space which minimise a fitness function for a given dataset. PopPK models are evaluated using NONMEM which estimates popPK parameter values and measures the data fit by the NONMEM objective function value (OFV) which is $-2 \log$ likelihood. Fitness was defined as the sum of OFV and a custom penalty function⁵ which penalised biologically implausible popPK models with abnormal parameter estimates. The search strategy followed our previous work⁵ where for each dataset we ran 4 generations of Bayesian optimisation with a population of 40 models per generation followed by an exhaustive local search algorithm. Both optimisation algorithms process the numerical features which are translated into a NONMEM configuration file by PyDarwin for the evaluation step.

PyDarwin defines a parameter space using a template text file for fixed elements and a JSON tokens file for the variable features. Variable features or tokens can be referenced

within the fixed template file or within other feature values. If a feature is referenced within the template, it will be active for every model configuration, but features referenced within other features values are conditionally active only when that feature value is selected. A simplified template and tokens file is shown in Figure 1. Here a feature for the number of compartments (NUM_CMT) is always active as it is referenced in the template file but the option to estimate inter-individual variability on the volume of the second compartment (OMEGA_V2) is only relevant for if NUM_CMT selects a 2-compartment model.

Fig. 1. Simplified example of the popPK parameter space. The fixed elements of the NONMEM configuration file are given in the template file on the left and the tokens file on the right describes potential feature values. When PyDarwin generates a configuration file for each candidate model, the template file is used as a base with curly brackets indicating the variable elements to be added based on the feature vector. Here the features are NUM_CMT and OMEGA_V2. For this example, each feature has 2 possible values shown in red and green. NUM_CMT is referenced within the template so is always active. OMEGA_V2 is only referenced within the 2nd value of NUM_CMT where a 2-compartment model is selected.

We propose an algorithm to flag active features using the feature vector and parameter space definition which can run within the optimisation process. For the active feature algorithm, we map the parameter space as a graph where each node represents an individual feature, and directed edges illustrate hierarchical (parent-child) relationships along with the activation conditions for child features. The graph can be generated prior to running the optimisation algorithms as the parameter space is static. During optimisation, a breadth-first search algorithm is used to traverse this graph for each candidate feature vector and determine which of the conditionally activated features are active. The parameter space graph is generated using string matching on the template and token files to map the nodes and edges. Figure 2a visualises this graph for the simple example model space shown in Figure 1 where feature 0 (NUM_CMT) references feature 1 (OMEGA_V2) which creates a directed edge from the parent to child feature. The graphs in Figure 2 show features referenced in the template which are active for all model configurations marked in red. Figure 2b shows the same graph for the full 17-feature parameter space. For our model space, there was only a single level of hierarchy with features 0 (number of compartments) and 9 (absorption model) controlling activation of child features. This approach could generalize to any level of hierarchy, a simple test with a toy model space featuring 2 levels of hierarchy is given in a notebook here, github.com/samjrrr/constrained_optimisation_poppk.

Leveraging the active feature detection algorithm, we adapted Bayesian optimisation and exhaustive local search algorithms with simple constraints to avoid evaluating duplicate configurations. For Bayesian optimisation, candidates are suggested using negative expected improvement, we filter duplicate configurations and replace them with new un-evaluated candidates for a fixed population size per generation. For local search, we simply filter duplicate models to reduce the total number of evaluations. By default, search algorithms within PyDarwin are unconstrained and unaware of the redundant configurations. We compare the default unconstrained search to a modified procedure with constraints. Search algorithms were evaluated for popPK model discovery across multiple clinical datasets from phase 1 trials (for the drugs camizestrant, osimertinib, olaparib, and tixagevimab/cilgavimab).

Fig. 2. Graph representation of the parameter space. The features in red are included in the base template and active for every model configuration, all other features are conditionally active. The directed edges show parent to child relationships. a: Graph for the simple example in Figure 1, b: Graph for the full 17 feature parameter space.

3 Results

Model structures were discovered automatically using constrained and unconstrained algorithms. Structures are presented for each dataset with comparison to published models in addition to non-functional metrics such as the number of models evaluated. For all four datasets, the constrained algorithms were found to reduce NONMEM evaluations and search time as shown in Figure 3. NONMEM evaluations were reduced by up to 47% (for osimertinib) and 36% on average across the four datasets. Search time reduced by up to 18% (for camizestrant) and 12% on average. Average model evaluations and search time are given from 5 repeat search runs.

Fig. 3. a: Average model evaluations (n=5) for each dataset during model search, b: Average search time (n=5) for each dataset during model search. For both a and b unconstrained and constrained approaches are compared.

For each dataset, the optimisation algorithms identified a top model structure by minimising a fitness function that considered both data fit and biological plausibility⁵. Whilst the number of evaluations was reduced with the constrained approach, there was no impact on the top model structures which were identical across all datasets for both the constrained and unconstrained approaches. The automatically discovered structures performed on par with manually developed structures from literature and were found to share 15/17 structural features on average. Differences found in the discovered structures led to improved fitness and reduced OFV values by 5% compared to the literature-derived structures on the tested data.

4 Conclusion

We present a constrained search approach for discovering popPK models by adapting Bayesian optimisation and exhaustive search algorithms. Across an evaluation of phase 1 clinical data, this approach was found to reduce model evaluation by up to 47% and search time by up to 18%. This method facilitates automated popPK development in complex, generic model spaces while reducing computational cost and search time. Automated approaches could significantly accelerate the structure development stage of popPK model building for pharmacometricians. We expect that the demonstrated reduction in compute time and cost, achieved through algorithmic constraints, will further the operational adoption of AI-supported popPK development.

5 References

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6 Code availability

Code for this report is made available at:
https://github.com/samjrrr/constrained_optimisation_poppk